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of **EXPRESSION**
A Creative Folio

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Divulge Now or Maybe Later

I saw myself languishing, forced to pretend,
Thinking I bore a Hercules knot inside.
I long to hold back; to stop is my intent,
For letting go is an uphill, painful ride.

But denial alone is never enough,
Closed eyes still see clasped hands in the field.
Two swans dancing through moments soft and rough,
And doves in the air refuse to conceal.

I am restless within this fleeting hour,
Unable to imagine confession.
Yet your scent leaves me grateful for its power;
May this enamored heart earn your impression?

Would you smile if I spoke honestly to thee?
Or should I wait, restrained and patiently?